

The Church of the Holy Sepulchre

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This church, located in the Christian quarter of the old city of Jerusalem (Israel), serves as the architectural monument commemorating the salvific events associated with the final days of Jesus' life. Consecrated in 335, and renovated repeatedly over the centuries, the church encompasses the traditional locations of Christ's crucifixion as well as his burial and subsequent resurrection. Its building was part of a broader building programme, instituted by Emperor Constantine (d.377) which saw the construction of a number of Christian churches in key sacred locations in Palestine. In its earliest form, it comprised two separate structures: the Rotunda, a circular building enclosing a smaller monument known as the Aedicule, and the Basilica of Constantine which stood to the East. The church however suffered numerous destructions which altered its fabric. Chief amongst these was its destruction in 1009 on orders of Fatimid Caliph al-Hakim (985-1021) which led to its reconstruction initially during the 11th century, but in the main during the period of the crusader Kingdom of Jerusalem (1099-1291). The building's current form is mainly the result of this reconstruction, completed in the Gothic style between the 1140s and the 1160s, though it has been subject to numerous, significant repairs since that date. The Rotunda remains the main part of the church and encloses the most sacred element of the structure. The Aedicule, a smaller monument contained within the Rotunda and rebuilt in 1555, was constructed over a 1st century CE rock-cut tomb, dug away from original quarry which it seems to have been a part. The empty tomb is believed to be that of Christ and is venerated by many Christian denominations as the location of Christ's resurrection from the dead. The south of the Church contains a chapel, reached by a series of steps, commemorating the place of Calvary or Golgotha, and thus the site of Christ's crucifixion. This chapel in turn sits atop further chapel in which the rock of Golgotha can be seen (sometimes recognised as the burial place of Adam). To the east of the Church, surrounding the choir, are a series of other chapels, including the Prison of Christ, the Chapel of Flagellation, the Chapel of Crowning with Thorns, and the subterranean chapel of St Helena which commemorates the site where the Empress Helena (d.330) miraculously discovered the resting place of the True Cross. All these locations play a significant role in historical and contemporary commemorations of Christ's passion and resurrection. In recent times, the Church has undergone major renovation works, particularly during the period of the British Mandate (1918-1948) and since the 1960s, though this latest phase was completed in 2017. Today it is held in reverence by many of Christianity's denominations. It is controlled jointly by groups representing the Roman Catholic, Greek Orthodox, Armenian Orthodox, Coptic, Syrian, and Ethiopian churches whose ownership is managed through an agreement known as the Status Quo which gives each group certain rights over different parts of the building. It is widely considered Christianity's most sacred place.

Date Range: 335 CE - 2022 CE

Region: The Church of the Holy Sepulchre

Region tags: Israel, Jerusalem

The footprint of the current church

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Denys Pringle, *The Churches of the Crusader Kingdom of Jerusalem: A Corpus. Volume III: The City of Jerusalem*, (Cambridge: CUP, 2010), pp.6-72
- Source 2: Martin Biddle, *The Tomb of Christ*, (Stroud, UK: Sutton Publishing, 1999)
- Source 3: Shinnon Gibson and Joan E. Taylor, *Beneath the Church of the Holy Sepulchre, Jerusalem: The Archaeology and Early History of Traditional Golgotha*, (London: Palestine Exploration Fund, 1994)

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.britannica.com/place/Holy-Sepulchre>
- Source 1 Description: Britannica encyclopaedic entry on the Church of the Holy Sepulchre

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Type of excavation:

- Scientific

Years of excavation:

- Year range: 1960s-1980s

Name of excavation

- Official or descriptive name: Excavations in connection restoration projects

Notes: The site has been the subject of numerous archaeological investigations since the 19th century (and before to some extent). A series of architectural and archaeological investigations took place during the 1960s and 1980s as part of various renovation projects. The books by Martin Biddle and by Shinnon Gibson and Joan E. Taylor (cited above) outline the results of the excavations. The restoration of the Edicule was completed in 2017.

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

- Other [specify]: Rock cut tomb

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– No

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

↳ Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– No

↳ Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– Yes

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– Yes

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

Notes: The Church itself is relatively self-contained, but if the site is intimately connected with other religious structures in the vicinity and internally represents a multi-layered sacred space with elements which might consider distinct from each other (the Tomb of Christ or Edicule, Calvary, the chapel of St Helena) all connected by the same structure.

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

–Other [specify]: Both communal and individual

– Memorial

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

Notes: An original series of structures were built over this site in the 4th century but the site has been expanded, rebuilt and renovated throughout history with key points being: the 7th century reconstruction following the sack of Jerusalem in 614; the 11th century reconstruction following the destruction of the site on the orders of the Fatimid Caliph al-Hakim in 1009; the 12th renovations and expansion of the site during the crusader period (during which the building took its modern form); the rebuilding of the Edicule in 1555; rebuilding work in from 1719-1720; the reconstruction of the dome between 1863-1868 following an earthquake; the repair and reinforcement of the building between 1934 and 1947 following further earthquakes; and the contemporary restoration of the building completed in phases between the 1960s and 2017.

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

–Other [specify]: By fire in 614; intentionally in 1009; it has also been damaged by fire, invasion, or earthquakes throughout its history but has been subsequently rebuild or repaired in each instance.

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

- For religious reasons
- As the result of war
- As the result of pillage

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:
– Natural phenomena

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:
– Yes

↳ In antiquity
– Periodically

↳ In modernity
– Post-Renaissance

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:
– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:
– Yes [specify]: Jesus Christ

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:
– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:
– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:
– Field doesn't know

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:
A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.
– Yes

↳ Specify

– King or emperor

Notes: The original 4th century structures were built following instructions given by Emperor Constantine.

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

↳ Groups:

– Specialized labourers/craftspeople

Notes: It's hard to identify who was involved in the construction and reconstruction of the church at various stages, but some elements speak to the involvement of specialized labourers and craftspeople.

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Other [specify]: The death, burial and resurrection of Christ, including various sites associated with his Passion

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

Notes: Various groups and individuals have contributed to the building and rebuilding of the site over the centuries.

↳ Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– Yes

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: Very difficult to attribute motives to its establishment.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

Notes: The Aedicule, which contains the tomb of Christ, is built over a rock cut tomb.

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

– Percentage: 100

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– I don't know

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– I don't know

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– I don't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– I don't know

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– No

↳ Sand

– No

↳ Clay

– No

↳ Plaster

– No

↳ Wood

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– I don't know

↳ Grass

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

Notes: Several elements of the building were created using the remains of previous structures located on and around the site.

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– No

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– I don't know

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– No

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– Yes

↳ Statues of humans:

– Yes

Notes: There is a statue of the Empress Helena in the chapel of St Helena which commemorates the location where she reportedly discovered the cross of Christ.

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– No

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– I don't know

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– Yes

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– Yes

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– Yes

↳ Mosaics representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– Yes

↳ Mosaics representing mythological narratives:

– Yes

↳ Mosaics representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– No

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]
– Yes

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:
– No

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)
– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)
– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)
– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)
– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife
– Yes

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)
– Yes

↳ Humans
– Yes

↳ Supernatural narratives

– Yes

↳ Human narratives

– Yes

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– Yes

Notes: Though it should be noted that the tomb is in fact empty, the emptiness of the tomb being one of its main attractions (as a symbol of Christ's resurrection).

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Notes: The site was previously the burial place for the Kings of Jerusalem (Godfrey of Bouillon [d.1100], Baldwin I [d.1118], Baldwin II [d.1131], Fulk of Anjou [d.1143], Baldwin III [1130-1163], Amalric I [1136-1174], Baldwin IV [d.1185], Baldwin V [1177/8-1186]) but the tombs have since been lost or destroyed.

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Notes: This is, of course, an incredibly complex and difficult question, depending greatly on your theological perspective and trinitarian position. The site commemorates the burial and resurrection of God the Son, Jesus Christ. 'No' has been selected here on two grounds: (1) that the site commemorates God the Son, rather than God the Father, though the difference here is perhaps merely a case of nuance, and (2) that God the Son is no longer physically present owing to his resurrection.

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Notes: The site, being a functioning Christian pilgrimage church, operates in the much the same way as any other, aside from its greater significance.

↳ In dreams:

– No

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Notes: Though see note above. The response here may change depending on your opinion about Christ's nature.

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– No

Ritual and Performance

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– No

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– No

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– I don't know

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– optional (common)

↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:

– No

↳ Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:

– No

↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Are festivals present:

– No

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Notes: This is not a primary function of the site, nor is well known for healing, but with any Christian pilgrimage location the possibility of visting the site in search of healing and successfully receiving it cannot be ruled out.

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Notes: The ritual in question is the Holy Fire ritual which occurs at Easter and involves the miraculous appearance of a flame within the Sepulchre itself and its distribution to participants.

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: 2500

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: Large-scale (the Holy Fire ritual): once per year. Small-scale (mass, procession, etc.): regularly

- ↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:
 - Yes
- ↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:
 - Yes
- ↳ Are there synchronic practices:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:
 - No

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

- ↳ Present full time
 - Yes
- ↳ Present part time
 - No
- ↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:
 - Yes
- ↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:
 - No
- ↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:
 - No

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– Yes

Notes: Religious communities (usually monastic) from a whole range of Catholic and Orthodox Christian denominations are present at the site and the use of the site, and who is allowed where, carefully managed and controlled. The primary custodians of the site are currently the members of the Catholic Church, the Greek Orthodox church and the Armenian Orthodox church. But other churches are present, and the current Status Quo does not represent how things have always been historically.

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Yes

↳ Is a bureaucracy present permanently:

– Yes

↳ Is a bureaucracy present on a temporary or seasonal basis:

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Yes

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– Yes

Notes: The Gospel accounts of Christ's Crucifixion and Resurrection are all connected with this place (see Matthew 27.11-28.10; Mark 15-16.8; Luke 23-24.12; John 19-20.18)

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they written at this place:

– No

↳ Are they oral:

– No

↳ Is there a story associated with the origin and/or construction of this place:

– Yes

↳ Are there religious specialists in charge of interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

↳ Are the scriptures part of the building/place:

– No

Bibliography

General References

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